

Review Article

A Comprehensive Review On High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 31 Dec 2023

Accepted: 04 Jan 2024

Published: 10 Jan 2024

Keywords:

Chromatography, HPLC, compounds, analytical.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.10477121

ABSTRACT

A collection of techniques called chromatography are employed to extract constituents from a mixture. This approach is divided into two phases; stationary and moveable. The basis for the constituent separation is the variation in the partition coefficients between the two phases. The Greek words "graphein" (to write) and "chroma" (color) are the origin of the word "chromatography". High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is an essential technology for determining the quality and quantity of pharmaceutical and environmental samples. It is the most flexible, safe, trustworthy, and efficient chromatographic method available for assessing the caliber of pharmaceutical components. Each component in a mixture can be identified, quantified, and separated using the analytical chemistry technique of high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC; formerly known as high-pressure liquid chromatography). A liquid is used as the mobile phase in HPLC, one type of liquid chromatography. Reversed-phase HPLC is the type most frequently employed. The mobile phase is relatively polar in a reversed-phase system, while the stationary phase is comparatively non-polar. The instruments used in HPLC analysis include a solvent reservoir, pump, injector, column, detector, integrator, or acquisition and display system, and detector. The system's brain is the column where separation occurs. Among other things, HPLC is useful for identifying, measuring, and resolving compounds.

INTRODUCTION

The techniques used to distinguish, identify, and measure the chemical components present in complex mixtures are referred to as chromatography. Like spectroscopy, this approach

is popular and very successful for preparative as well as analytical techniques. This method can be used to create pure chemicals of the highest quality. According to its definition, chromatography is the process of separating

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

mixture components according to how quickly a gaseous or liquid mobile phase moves them through a stationary phase (column) [1].

High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC):

HPLC is a specific kind of column chromatography used to identify, separate, and quantify the active compounds [2]. Three main parts make up an HPLC system: a stationary phase (column filled with packing material), a pump that moves one or more mobile phases through the column, and a detector that shows the molecules retention times. Retention time is influenced by the interactions that occur between the stationary phase, the molecules under investigation, and the solvent used [3]. The sample for analysis is delayed by specific chemical or physical interactions with the stationary phase after being added in small quantities to the stream of mobile phase. The kind of analyte and the composition of the mobile and stationary phases affect the retardation. A given analyte's retention time is the length of time it takes for it to elute, or leave, the column. Most miscible combinations of organic liquids or water are used as solvents (acetonitrile and methanol are the most popular ones) [2, 3]. The separation procedure called gradient elution is employed to alter the composition of the mobile phase in the course of the analysis [4]. The gradient divides the mixtures of analytes according to their affinity for the current mobile phase. The gradient, solvents, and additives selected depend on the characteristics of the analyte and stationary phase.

Principle:

Purification takes place in a column that separates a stationary phase from a mobile phase. The stationary phase of a separation column is a granular material with extremely small porous particles. Conversely, a solvent or solvent mixture that is forced through the separation column at

high pressure is known as the mobile phase. Sample loops, which are tiny tubes or stainless-steel capillaries, are connected to valves that allow the sample to be fed into the mobile phase flow from the pump to the separation column. The different components of the sample migrate across the column at different speeds because they are held to varying degrees as a result of interactions with the stationary phase. Following their passage through the column, the various compounds are identified by an appropriate detector and transmitted as a signal to the computer's HPLC software. After this process, a chromatogram that can be used with the computer's HPLC software to identify and quantify the various compounds is produced [5, 6, 7].

History:

Before the invention of HPLC, scientists employed traditional liquid chromatographic methods. Liquid chromatographic methods are inefficient because of the dependence of solvent flow rate on gravity. It can take several hours, or even days, to finish a separation. It was believed that gas stage partition and the study of highly polar high atomic weight biopolymers were not feasible, even though liquid chromatography (LC) was at the time more effective. Because the solutes were thermally unstable, some organic chemists found that GC was unsuccessful. It was therefore expected that other techniques would soon propel HPLC forward. In the 1960s, building on the work of Martin and Synge in 1941, Cal Giddings, Josef Huber, and others predicted that LC could be operated in the high-efficiency mode by lowering the pressing molecule measurement well below the standard LC and GC level of 150 μm and using pressure to increase the versatile stage velocity. These expectations were the subject of much investigation and development in the 1960s and early 1970s. Early efforts were made to enhance LC particles, and the creation of the externally

permeable molecule Zipax proved positive for HPLC technology. Throughout the 1970s, a lot of advancements in equipment and machinery were produced. Experts originally constructed a simple HPLC system using injectors and pumps. The reason gas amplifier pumps were ideal was that they didn't require release free seals or check valves for excellent accuracy and steady flow, and they operated at a constant pressure. The history of HPLC is primarily the story of the development of molecular technology, even though equipment advancements played a big part. Since the introduction of permeable layer particles to boost efficacy, there has been a constant trend towards smaller molecules. However, new issues surfaced as molecule sizes decreased. It is anticipated that the disadvantage of the unnecessary pressure drop will be the challenge of uniformly pressing extremely fine materials and moving diverse liquid through the segment. Generally, each time the molecule size is fully reduced, another cycle of instrument advancement should occur to manage the pressure [8–13].

Operation:

In a special extremely tiny volume; usually microliters, the sample mixture that will be separated and blended is added to the stream of mobile section that permeates the column. Due to certain physical interactions with the adsorbent, the sample is split into segments that pass through the phase at different rates (also known as stationary stage). The composition of its movable part and compound structure dictates the speed of each constituent. The time at which a selected analytical elutes, or rises out of the column, is referred to as the retention time. The retention time evaluated under specific conditions may be a characteristic that is standard for a particular analysis [14–18]. Adsorbents with various molecular sizes and surface properties are available in a variety of column configurations

("surface science"). Action resolution, or the degree of division between successive analyses ascending up out of the column, is sometimes improved by using higher operational pressure also known as "backpressure". When packing materials with small molecular sizes are used. Particles of something can be hydrophobic or polar. Water and other natural solvents, such as any mixable combination of water (acetonitrile and methanol being the most generally recognized area unit), are combined in basic mobile phases. There are HPLC systems that use non-water-soluble mobile phases. To help with the separation of the sample portions, the aqueous phase of the mobile section may contain acids (such as formic, element, or trifluoroacetic corrosive) or salts. The mobile sections composition may alter (also known as "inclination extraction mode") or stay the same throughout the chromatographic analysis ("isocratic extraction mode"). Isocratic extraction usually works well for pattern elements that are no longer completely exceptional in their inclination for the stationary stage. The cellular area's employer in gradient extraction commonly fluctuates from low to extremely high eluting enormous. The mobile section's eluting quality is indicated by analytical maintenance durations; a high eluting quality results in speedy extraction. The structure of the mobile section (also called eluent) is determined by the stationary stage's stationary stage and the strength of connections between entirely independent example pieces ("analyses") (e.g. hydrophobic connections in turned about stage HPLC). Analyses split between the two during the detachment operation in the sample based on their choice for the stationary and mobile stages. This procedure is comparable to a liquid-liquid extraction, with the exception that it is continuous as opposed to stepwise. Extra hydrophobic components may wash (slip off the column) late in this scenario, during varying

amounts of upper eluting quality, when the mobile stage becomes more densely packed with acetonitrile [19–27].

Types of HPLC:

The types of HPLC that are commonly employed in analysis depend on whether a phase system is used in the process [3, 4].

Normal phase chromatography:

Analytes are divided based on polarity using this method, which is also referred to as Normal phase HPLC (NPHPLC). In NP-HPLC, both non-polar mobile phase and polar stationary phase are employed. The polar analyte was bound by the polar stationary phase after it interacted with it. Stronger adsorption forces and a longer elution time are the outcomes of increased analyte polarity and interaction with the polar stationary phase.

Reversed phase chromatography:

The reversed phases of HPLC (RPHPLC or RPC) consist of an aqueous, moderately polar mobile phase and a non-polar stationary phase. RPC operates on the principle of hydrophobic interactions, which arise from repulsive forces between a polar eluent, the often-non-polar analyte, and the non-polar stationary phase. The analyte's affinity for the stationary phase after interaction with the ligand in the aqueous eluent is proportional to the contact surface area around its non-polar region.

Size exclusion chromatography (SEC):

A form of chromatography that mainly uses size to separate particles is sometimes referred to as gel filtration chromatography or gel permeation chromatography. It is also useful in determining the tertiary and quaternary structures of amino acids and proteins. The molecular weight of polysaccharides is commonly ascertained using this technique.

Ion exchange chromatography:

Retention is driven by the attraction between solute ions and charged sites attached to the

stationary phase. Ions with same charge are not included. This kind of chromatography is commonly used for a variety of purposes, including high-pH anion-exchange chromatography of carbohydrates and oligosaccharides, protein ion-exchange chromatography, ligand-exchange chromatography, and water purification [3, 4].

Bio-affinity chromatography:

A method of separation predicated on a specific, reversible interaction between proteins and ligands. In a bio-affinity matrix, proteins that interact with the ligands attached to the column are held onto a solid support by ligands that are covalently bound to it. There are two ways in which proteins attached to a bio affinity column can be eluted:

- A particular elution is one in which the contact protein with the column-bound substrate is weakened by a change in pH, salt, etc.
- Biospecific elution involves competing with column-bound ligand for free ligand by adding it to the elution buffer.
- Due to the interaction's selectivity, bioaffinity chromatography can produce extremely high purification levels in a single step (10–1000 times).

Instrumentation:

The fundamental HPLC apparatus is depicted in figure 1.

1. Solvent Reservoir:

A glass reservoir holds the materials used in the mobile stage. The dissolvable, or versatile, stage in high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is generally a mixture of polar and non-polar liquid segments, the specific fixations of which are dependent on the specimen's arrangement

Fig. 1: Instrumentation - High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)

2. Pump:

A pump draws the adaptable stage from the dissolvent reservoir and passes it via the detector and column of the framework. Working weights of up to 42000 kPa (about 6000 psi) can be achieved, depending on a number of factors such as column measurements, the stationary stage's molecule size, the versatile stage's synthesis, and the stream rate.

3. Sample Injector:

The injector may be an automated infusion framework or a single infusion. An injector for an HPLC system should provide high weight (up to 4000 psi) and high reproducibility infusion of the liquid specimen within the range of 0.1–100 mL of volume.

4. Columns:

Columns are typically between 50 and 300 mm long, with an interior distance across of between 2 and 5 mm. They are typically constructed of cleaned stainless steel. Usually, a stationary stage containing molecules ranging in size from 3 to 10 μm is fed into them. Columns that have inner spacing of less than 2 mm are commonly referred to as microbore HPLC columns. In an ideal scenario, the temperature of the column and the portable stage should remain constant during the examination.

5. Detector:

As the analytes elute from the chromatographic column, the HPLC indicator, which is positioned toward the end of the column, separates them. UV spectroscopy, fluorescence, mass spectrometry, and electrochemical indicators are often used finders.

6. Data Collection Devices:

Signals from the indicator can be recorded on electronic integrators or outline recorders, which vary in terms of their multifaceted quality and ability to analyze, store, and reprocess chromatographic data. The PC arranges for the identifier's reaction with each component and loads it into a chromatograph that is remarkably easy to see and understand [28, 29, 30].

7. Degasser:

Gases that are invisible to the human eye, including oxygen, may be present in the eluent used for LC analysis. An unstable baseline results from the presence of gas in the eluent, which is recognized as noise. The most widely utilized techniques include heating and stirring, aspirator use, distillation systems, and sparging (bubbling of inert gas). Nevertheless, the procedure is inconvenient, and the gas will gradually dissolve back into the solvent if it is left for an extended amount of time (such as during a lengthy

investigation). Special polymer membrane tubing is used by degassers to extract gases. The polymer tube's surface is covered in many tiny pores that let air pass through but keep liquids from passing through. This tubing developed pressure differences inside and outside of it (higher inside the tubing) when it was placed under a low-pressure container. This distinction made it possible for the dissolved gas to pass through the pores and be expelled. The degasser is more efficient and convenient to use online than traditional batch type degassing. A degasser is a feature of many modern HPLC unit systems [31, 32, 33].

8. Column Heater:

The temperature of the column frequently has a significant impact on the LC separation. Maintaining constant temperature conditions is crucial for producing repeatable results. Additionally, higher temperatures (50 to 80°C) can yield greater resolutions for particular analyses, such as those involving sugar and organic acid. Even when the sample is evaluated at room temperature, maintaining a steady temperature is crucial for reproducible findings. It's possible that slight temperature variations lead to various separation outcomes. As a result, columns are typically stored within column heaters, or column ovens.

Applications:

HPLC can be used to find information about a compounds identity, quantity, and resolution. Preparative HPLC is the term used to describe the separation and purification of substances. In contrast, the main objective of analytical HPLC is to obtain more information about the sample substance. The following are the main applications:

A. Pharmaceuticals:

Large-performance liquid chromatography offers a large linear dynamic range along with consistent

quantitative precision and accuracy, making it possible to detect API and related chemicals in a single run. One useful technique for producing solid dosage forms is to disperse samples in water or aqueous solutions that have been altered with methanol or acetonitrile. Using HPLC, chiral substances can be divided into their distinct enantiomers in a variety of ways. Among these is the creation of diastereomers using precolumn derivatization. As stationary phases, you may also use specially designed columns with chiral moieties or cyclodextrins. In summary, reverse phase HPLC is the most popular quantitative analysis method in the pharmaceutical sector. The following are typical application areas for pharmaceutical analysis as shown in figure 2.

Fig. 2: Pharmaceuticals application of HPLC

B. Foods:

High-performance liquid chromatography has produced a number of desirable advantages in the field of food analysis. Food matrices are often complicated, which makes the process of extracting analytes challenging. Traditional extraction and analysis methods do not provide the required levels of accuracy and precision, and concerns are further complicated by the fact that both undesired and desired components are frequently present in trace amounts. HPLC offers practical solutions because of the many stationary

phase and mobile phase options. Typical uses for foods include;

- Pesticides with residuals, like monochrotophos and 2, 4-D.
- Antioxidants including TBHQ, BHA, and BHT;
- Fat-soluble vitamins (A, D, E, and K).
- Antibiotic residue.
- Sugars: glucose, fructose, maltose, and other saccharides;
- Water-soluble vitamins (B-complex vitamins, such as B1, B2, B3, B6, Folic acid, Pantothenic acid, B12, and Vitamin C).
- Steroids and flavonoids
- Cholesterol and sterols
- Mycotoxins, such as ochratoxin, Alfatoxins B1, B2, G1, G2, M1, M2, and others.
- Aspartame and other artificial sweeteners; • Amino acids.

C. Production:

HPLC has various applications in the fields of clinical research and laboratory science. It is a typical strategy used in pharmaceutical development since it is a dependable way to attain and guarantee product purity. Although high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) can produce extremely high-quality (purity) goods, it is not always the primary technique used in the synthesis of bulk pharmaceutical substances. According to the European Pharmacopeia, HPLC is only used in 15.5% of syntheses. On the other hand, 44% of the US Pharmacopeia's syntheses involve it. Considering that large-scale HPLC analysis can be costly, this could be the outcome

of several time and budgetary constraints. Sadly, there is a direct correlation between cost and increased specificity, precision, and accuracy in HPLC.

D. Research:

Similar methods can be applied to the detection of potential therapeutic candidates' concentrations, such as those found in asthma and antifungal drugs. This approach is undoubtedly effective for observing many species in collected samples; nevertheless, standard solutions must be used in order to identify the species. Purity is used to confirm the results of synthesis reactions because it is important in this type of research.

E. Medical:

Although nutritional analysis is more closely related to this function, HPLC can be utilized for pharmaceutical analysis in medical settings. Urine is the most commonly utilized medium for measuring drug concentrations, whereas blood serum is the sample used for most medical HPLC tests. HPLC has been contrasted with alternative methods, particularly immunoassays, in order to identify chemicals relevant to clinical research. In one case, the competitive protein binding assays (CPBA) and high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) were tested for their ability to detect vitamin D. Although this CPBA was found to be useful in detecting vitamin D insufficiency in children, its sensitivity and specificity were found to only account for 40% and 60%, respectively, of the HPLC's capacity. Although HPLC is an expensive tool, its accuracy is practically unrivaled. Additional HPLC applications are displayed in Table 1 [34–38].

Environmental Applications	Application in Forensics	Application in Clinical Trial
Detection of phenolic compounds in drinking water.	Quantification of drugs in biological samples.	Urine analysis, antibiotics analysis in blood

Bio-monitoring of pollutants.	Identification of steroids in blood, urine, etc.	Analysis of bilirubin, biliverdin in hepatic disorders.
	Forensic analysis of textile dyes	Detection of endogenous neuropeptides in the extracellular fluid of the brain, etc.
	Determination of cocaine and other drugs of abuse in blood, urine, etc.	

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the HPLC technology must be used to separate and quantify the principal drug from any reactive impurities. Liquid is used as the mobile phase in HPLC. Reversed-phase HPLC is the most often utilized type of HPLC. When the mobile phase is significantly polar and the stationary phase is comparatively non-polar, this condition is referred to as reversed-phase. Non-polar molecules will therefore be retained longer and be stored in greater quantities than polar chemicals. In normal phase HPLC, the mobile phase is typically non-polar, but the stationary phase is somewhat polar. These components are kept away from one another by column packing, which entails a variety of chemical and/or physical interactions between the molecules of the components and the packing particles. These separated components are detected by a low-through device (detector) that measures their quantity at the departure of a column. Although HPLC and LC function similarly in theory, HPLC is much faster, more sensitive, and easier to use. This detector's output is referred to as a "HPLC." Furthermore, it is the most trustworthy analytical method that is widely applied to do both quantitative and qualitative evaluations of medication products as well as evaluate the stability of drug goods.

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HOW TO CITE: Chetna Malwal, P. B. Jadhav, Vinod Bairagi, A Comprehensive Review on High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 1, 125-134. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10477121>